

IMPACT OF MODERNISATION ON THE DRESS STYLE OF FEMALE YOUNG ADULTS IN IMAGBON VILLAGE

Sunday, Kehinde Shakiru

Department of Sociology and Anthropology
University of Uyo, Uyo

Wilson, Nsikanabasi Udofia

Department of Sociology and Anthropology
University of Uyo, Uyo

Abstract

The increased modernisation in the global era largely propagated by social media platforms and celebrity/influencer lifestyles have popularize western dress patterns that have been copied by young adults in Imagbon village in Odogbulu Local Government Area (LGA) of Ogun State to the detriment of traditional practices. This paper aimed to assess the impact of modernisation on female young adults' dress pattern in Imagbon Village with a view to proposing recommendations towards addressing associated challenges. The method of data gathering adopted for this paper work was qualitative, involving in-depth interviews with 8 young female adults and elders in Imagbon Village. Findings revealed that the original traditional attires designed for female young adults in the area include Iro Ati Buaba, Aso-Oke and Ofi, but many young female adults have abandoned these dresses and started wearing miniskirts, pump, trousers, sleeveless gowns, and even dress without putting on any form of underwear, which is promoting disappearance of native dress codes, outright abuse of traditional attires, infiltration of native culture by foreign culture, which also occasioned cases of immorality, sexual abuse, fornication and loss of original cultural orientations. The paper recommends, among others, that traditional institutions come up with by-laws reintroducing dress codes according to customs and traditions and generate funds for mass enlightenment of people, especially young female adults across communities, and set up a special task force to implement all by-laws forbidding the use of dresses not known to culture, who should arrest violators and ensure that they are made to face the punishment as may be prescribed by the traditional rulers.

Keywords: Modernization, female young adults, dress style.

Introduction

Fashion is an important aspect of human culture, forming identities, affecting perceptions, and reflecting societal ideals and changes. It is more than just clothing choices; it represents uniqueness, expresses social position, and reflects historical and cultural influences. Fashion has an incredible potential to affect how we perceive ourselves and others, shaping our interactions and societal responsibilities. Fashion, as a dynamic force, evolves in response to the world's ever-changing landscape, even as fashion fads come and go, reflecting altering values, technological breakthroughs, and global events. Every society in the world has a distinct fashion style that conveys symbolism and cultural significance (Ibiwoye, 2020).

The Yoruba people are well-known for their rich cultural legacy, including music, dance, religion, language, and fashion. In this modern era of Western dress acceptance, understanding the extent of change in dress pattern among Yoruba females and its implication is vital. Yoruba traditional clothing, when done properly, always makes a statement! In the magnificent realm of Yoruba fashion, culture and beauty mix seamlessly, resulting in stunning hues, textures, and designs (Olusesi, 2024). Yoruba women's traditional outfit includes the "buba" (blouse), "iro" (wrapper), "ipele" (shawl), and "gele" (headgear). The "buba" is a loose-fitting shirt with intricate decorations, but the "iro" in Yoruba is a wrapper wrapped around the waist that comes in a variety of materials and patterns. The "ipele" is a shawl worn around the waist. Gele, the headpiece, is intricately twisted into motifs that suit the outfit. It may also contain the "iborun," a lace-up shawl worn over the shoulders. The aso-oke contains these characteristics as well, however it is made of handwoven cotton and is primarily worn on special occasions (Olusesi, 2024). This attire is worn in traditional marriage ceremony (Paul and Peters, 2023).

However, the increased modernization in the global era largely propagated by social media platforms and celebrity/influencer lifestyles have popularize western dress patterns (Bassey et al (2023), that have been copied by young adults in Yoruba land, especially in Imagbon village in Odogbulu Local Government Area (LGA) of Ogun State, which is the focus of this paper.

Statement of the Problem

Nowadays, many young people, especially girls, dress in ways that do not conform to accepted decorum. This requires immediate action and required modifications, not only to preserve these cultural features, but also for decency. The appropriate method of dressing among the Yorubas prior to the influence of foreign culture and civilization, which degraded the dignity of the mode of dressing (Olawuni, 2022) need to be brought back. This is vital in light of changing societal trends, occasioned by globalization, and the repercussions of uprightness and culturally acceptable dressing mode (Olawuni, 2022). For example, young adults in Imagbon Village who are Yorubas imposing or assimilating western dress styles demonstrate that what is helpful to African clothing patterns has been abandoned in favour of foreign culture. Nowadays, it appears that young adults in Imagbon Village are unclear when to wear specific attire or which is proper, so they end up wearing dresses that expose their bodies, including sensitive areas. Such immoral clothing contributes to several crimes in our society. Rape, for example, is widespread among young people due to their public attire. However, no action has been taken to remedy this irregularity over the years.

Previously, studies on indecent dressing were conducted. Ogunsanya (2020) conducted a study titled Changing Patterns in Feeding, Dressing, and Naming among Yoruba in South-West Nigeria Since 1960. The primary goal of the research was to identify shifting patterns in several areas of Yoruba culture, such as feeding style, attire, and naming among the Yoruba people of Southwestern Nigeria. It is a descriptive survey with a sample size of 180 men and women aged 51 or older from various geographical locations. It was revealed that the Yoruba's feeding, clothing, and naming patterns alter gradually and steadily. It is advised that efforts be made to promote the people's cultural heritage. The study was however not restricted to young adult female dress style that has become a major issue in recent time, which is the major gap filled by this paper.

The adoption of Western-inspired dress patterns among young adults females in

Imagbon Village has needs urgent attention due to the consequences of indecent dressing including rape and cultural bastardization.

Objectives

The aim of this study is to assess the impact of modernization on female young adults' dress pattern in Imagbon Village with a view to proposing recommendations towards addressing associated challenges. Specific objectives are:

- i. Find out the nature of modern dress style among young female adults in Imagbon Village.
- ii. Determine how such change in dressing affect cultural heritage and its implication on female young adults.
- iii. Propose recommendations on how to address the effects of change in dress style from traditional to modernity on cultural heritage and young adults.

Conceptual Framework

Modernization. Modernisation, in sociology, refers to the transition from a traditional, rural, agrarian civilisation to a secular, urban, industrial society (Kumar, 2025). Modernisation in this context refers to the process of change in the dress style of young female adults in Imagbon Village.

Dress Style. 'Dress style' means the general style of what one wear (Cellio, 2012). In this paper, dress style refers to the pattern of dressing among young female adults in Imagbon Village.

Female Young Adults. Young adults, as used in this paper are females between the age of 18 – 25 years. The ages of 18 and 25 is a special developmental stage during which the young adult engages in important developmental activities that allow for self-discovery and identity construction (Arnett, 2004), which pave way for new decisions on dress style, occasioning the adoption of Western style at the expense of traditional style.

Theoretical Framework

The paper adopted evolutionary theory. Charles Darwin and Alfred Russel Wallace are the leading proponents of evolutionary theory, particularly natural selection. In 1858, Charles Darwin and Alfred Russel Wallace published a novel evolutionary hypothesis, which is detailed in Darwin's *On the Origin of Species* (1859). Darwin's theory, originally known as descent with modification, is today more often known as Darwinism or Darwinian Theory. The central tenet of evolutionary theory, especially as formulated by Charles Darwin, is that species evolve by a process known as natural selection. This means that creatures with traits better suited to their environment are more likely to survive and reproduce, passing on those advantageous characteristics to their offspring. These changes aggregate throughout time, resulting in biological diversification and the emergence of new species.

When applied to Africa's evolving dress patterns, evolutionary theory says that dress changes in response to a variety of elements such as cultural influences, social dynamics, and environmental conditions. This means that traditional clothing, which were originally solely utilitarian, have grown more expressive and diversified, reflecting a society's evolving values and aesthetics. Early African clothing was often made of natural materials such as bark cloth, raffia, and animal skins, which were gradually refined through weaving, dyeing, and embellishment. The addition of beads, shells, and other decorative elements increased the

complexity and aesthetic appeal of clothing.

The introduction of European and Asian textiles and styles has also influenced the evolution of African attire, particularly among young female adults in Imagbon Village. Africans have frequently adapted foreign materials and styles to their own cultural contexts, as evident among young female adults in Imagbon Village resulting in distinctive hybrid forms that no longer represent the real culture of Yoruba people in terms of dress style. The expansion of urban areas, as well as the influence of modern fashion trends, has increased the diversity of young female adults in Imagbon Village dress styles. Contemporary designers are looking for new methods to combine classic processes with current aesthetics.

Method

A survey research design was adopted for the study. The method of data gathering adopted for this work was qualitative research method. It specifically adopted the In-depth interview method to collect data from young female adults and elders in Imagbon Village. A total of five young female adults and 3 female elders are sample through purposive sampling techniques. The data was thematically analysed to arrive at a dependable conclusion.

Findings

In line with the three specific objectives of this paper, many primary and sub-themes were identified as indicated in the tables below:

Table 1.

Find out the nature of modern dress style among young female adults in Imagbon Village

Primary Theme	Secondary Themes	Sub-Themes
Nature of modern dress style among young female adults	Main traditional cultural dress styles	Iro ati Buba
		Aṣo-Oke
		Ofi
	Types of new dress styles	Miniskirts , pump, trousers
		Sleeveless gowns
		Dressing without under -wears

Source: Author (2025)

Table 1 reveals one primary theme, 2 secondary themes and 6 sub-themes. In earnest, there are three major traditional cultural dress styles applicable to young female adults in the traditional setting in Imagbon Village of Odogbolu LGA of Ogun State, which are Iro ati Buba – a two-piece garment consisting of a wrapper (Iro) and a loose-fitting blouse (Buba), Aṣo-Oke – a hand loomed cloth of different patterns and colours sewn into various styles, and Ofi – pure white yarned cloths, used as cover cloth, it can be sewn and worn. Speaking on this, an elderly women interviewed states:

We have our original traditional wears when we were young. Although, some of these dresses can be worn by adults, young ladies can sew them as their desire and they usually look good on us. For instance, Iro Ati Buba is well fitting for us then, and we usually swe Aso-Oke to any fitting size and wear. Till today, many young ladies still like to sew Aso-Oke and wear, and it usually looks good on them.

However, over the years these traditional dress styles have been replaced with modern dress styles among female young adults. Specifically, it was female young adults in Imagbon Village delight in wearing of western dress styles such as mini-skirts, pump – very short nicker, and trousers that was originally wore by only male among the people. An informant, an elderly woman notes:

Our young ladies no longer dress like we did. They now wear all manner of clothes that the watch from television which are actually not our culture. In fact, the wearing of trousers was not part of our culture but you can see that young ladies now wear trousers even to church. Another one that is most annoying is the wearing of very short skirt that almost exposes their private parts. It is really a troubling situation that must not be allowed to continue.

Another form modern dress style adopted by young female adults in Imagbon Village is the wearing of sleeveless gowns which come in different forms. According to one of the informants, a young female, “*This is a modern era and you don't expect me to be wearing traditional style of dress always; at least once in a while I can wear that to occasion, but now I prefer my Spaghetti (sleeveless gown).*”

Furthermore, the elderly informants greatly complained about young ladies now wearing clothes without under-wear which was not the case in the past. According to an elderly woman interviewed:

Something bad has actually happened in our community. The dress style has changed greatly among young adults, and it is actually looking like we no longer have culture. A situation where young ladies would dress seductively was never part of our culture. There is even this thing that girls no longer wear under-wears that we were proud of during our days. Hardly would you see a Yoruba woman without an under-wear in the past, but now young ladies were clothes without under-wear so that their buttocks can shake and attract men.

The findings above are consistent with those of Fadipe *et al.* (2024) study, which found that social media influence, a lack of moral upbringing, and a lack of parental supervision were the leading causes of indecent dressing in Nigeria.

Table 2.
Determine how such change in dressing affect cultural heritage and its implication on female young adults

Primary Theme	Secondary Themes	Sub-Themes
Effects of change in dressing pattern on cultural heritage and its female young adults	Cultural heritage	Disappearance of native dress code
		Abuse of traditional attire
		Infiltration of native culture
		Promotion of immorality
	Female young adults	Sexual abuse
		Fornication
		Loss of original cultural orientation

Source: Author (2025)

Table two shows 1 primary theme, two secondary themes and 7 sub-themes. Specifically, findings reveal that the change in dress style among female young adults in Imagbon Village greatly affected the cultural heritage and female young adults. Specifically, the situation has resulted in disappearance of native dress code, abuse of traditional attire, infiltration of native culture and promotion of immorality. One of the young adults interviewed notes:

I cannot lie; I know the situation has affected our cultural heritage because there is a gradual disappearance of traditional attires among us, the youths. For instance, I do not even know the original dresses that I am supposed to wear as a young girl based on my culture – my parents never taught me anything on this aspect. I only grow up to watch what others are wearing and I make my choices from the ones I see.

Buttressing this, another young girl interviewed states, “*I don't even know the clothes I am expected to wear as tradition demands. I do know it is affecting our original culture when it comes to dress code.*”

Another informant, an elderly woman says:

Our culture has been taken over by the western style of dressing, not only among the young ladies, but even adults. I have seen married women wear trousers, and this is completely not in line with our culture. That is why we have so many cases of immorality in our community today.

Furthermore, findings revealed that female young adults in Imagbon Village are also affected by the changing pattern of dress styles. Specifically, the situation has resulted in cases of sexual abuse, fornication and loss of original cultural orientation. According to an elderly woman interviewed, “*many young ladies are raped because they refuse to dress according to our custom, which recommend that they be properly covered.*”

A young lady interviewed notes:

I can't really talk much on the effects of change in dress style on young girls, but I have heard from several people that if I don't stop wearing some kinds of clothes, I could be raped. I also heard from one of my friends who was raped that her family blamed her

for wearing transparent clothes, which I think should not be the reason for anyone to rape a young lady.

Furthermore, an elderly woman interviewed notes:

You know these new dresses attract boys to these girls; that is why many of them fornicate in recent time. It was not so during our time. There is no way you will wear short clothes, and boys will not come for you; girls who do not have a strong mind usually fall for them. Also, many young ladies do not even know what our culture demand in terms of dressing, and that is why they wear whatever they feel, and now commit fornication that was not part of our tradition.

The above findings are consistent with the findings of Olorunda's (2022) study, which revealed the consequences of indecent dressing to include rape and prostitution and concluded that indecent dressing has detrimental effects on youth in southwest Nigeria.

Table 3.

Propose recommendations on how to address the effects of change in dress style from traditional to modernity on cultural heritage and female young adults

Primary Theme	Secondary Themes	Sub-Themes
How to address the effects of change in dress style on cultural heritage and female young adults	Cultural heritage	Strict instructions on adherence from traditional rulers
		Mass enlightenment using media platforms
		Sanctioning erring ladies
	Female young adults	Rehabilitation and counseling
		Parental guide
		Education in schools

Source: Author (2025)

Table 3 reveals 1 primary theme, 2 secondary themes and 6 sub-themes. Basically, findings revealed that the effects of change in dress style among young adults on cultural heritage and female young adults can be address in various ways. Specifically, many of the informants recommended that traditional rulers should give strict instructions that traditional attire should be worn by young ladies, and also ensure that communities embark on a mass enlightenment campaign on this using the media, while those who disobey such instructions should be punished as a deterrent to others. An elderly women interviewed states:

The only solution to this madness is for traditional institutions to seat up. We must not watch our culture degenerate – let there be strict instruction, telling young ladies to dress according to custom, and it should be implemented with clear sanctions on anyone who disobey.

A female young lady interviewed notes:

Like I said earlier, I don't even know the kind of clothes I should be wearing, so I think we need to be enlightened. The leaders should

ensure that the types of clothes that are expected to be used by girls of my age are communicated to them on time, so that even if they try to learn from the social media or any other means, they will know that there is a specified clothes to wear. Even if not all young ladies do not abide, there are some that will follow with what society teaches.

Furthermore, it was found that addressing the effects of changing dress styles on young women should involve rehabilitation and counselling for those already affected, and parents should try to guide their daughters on what to wear. Meanwhile, schools should aim to teach young women about cultural attire and its benefits. A young girl interviewed suggested, "I think they should make dressing code part of our education so that we can understand the value of using local clothes."

An elderly woman interviewed states:

I think the victims of rape and those who have gone deep in fornication need our support. They need to be reformed and allow to heal, so that others can learn from their mistakes and see how society show them love so that they can easily accept whatever we advise them to wear. I also think that the parents have a lot of work to do – they should instill discipline on their children, especially females and prevent them from dressing indecently in the name of modernity.

The findings are consistent with Mofoluwawo and Oyelade's (2012) recommendations that the implementation of a dress code and sanctions for defaulters, as seen in some universities, as well as the posting of posters and handbills preaching against indecent dressing on campus, could be effective measures to control indecent dressing in Nigeria's tertiary institutions.

Conclusion

Based on the data presented and discussed above, the paper concludes that there is high level of digression from the original and traditional dress styles among young female adults in Imagbon Village, Odogbolu LGA of Ogun State. The original traditional attires designed for female young adults include Iro Ati Buaba, Aso-Oke and Ofi, but many young female adults have abandoned these dresses and started wearing miniskirts, pump, trousers, sleeveless gowns, and even dress without putting on any form of underwear. Consequently, there seems to be disappearance of native dress codes and outright abuse of traditional attires. Also, it was found that there is huge deal of infiltration of native culture by foreign culture by the choice of dresses among young female adults who are seen to be promoting immorality, while the situation degenerates into sexual abuse, fornication and loss of original cultural orientations, and must not be allowed to fester.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the paper recommends the following:

- i. Traditional institutions should come up with by-laws reintroducing dress codes according to customs and traditions and generate funds for mass enlightenment of people, especially young female adults across communities. This can be achieved through partnering with both mainstream and social media platforms to spread the

- news of the acceptable dress styles on regular basis, especially during weekends.
- ii. Traditional institutions should also set up a special task force to implement all by-laws forbidding the use of dresses not known to culture. The task force should be made up of youths who are morally inclined with proven character, who should arrest violators and made to face the punishment as may be prescribed by the traditional rulers.
 - iii. Traditional institutions should partner with the government to raise funds for the rehabilitation and reformation of all female young adults affected by change in dress styles, maybe due to rape and temptation to go into temptation, in order to build the patriotic mind-set into them and cause them to change their negative attitude.

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